

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF LOGISTICS ACTIVITIES ON AGRICULTURE AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY IN ETHIOPIAN EXPORT-IMPORT PERSPECTIVES

¹Mekonin Abera Negeri, ²Sergey Evgenievich Barykin, ³Akram Odilovich Ochilov

¹Postgraduate student, Graduate School of Service and Trade, Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University, St. Petersburg, Russian Federation

²Deputy Director for Scientific Research and Development, Doctor of Economic Sciences, professor, Graduate School of Service and Trade, Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University, St. Petersburg, Russian Federation

³DSc., Professor, Karshi State University, 17 Kochabog, Karshi, 180119, Republic of Uzbekistan

¹ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2879-7459>

²ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9048-009X>

³ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-9254-188X>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15421470>

In the modern world, globalization and the rapid advancement of technology have an impact on both logistics and agriculture. In order to optimize the supply chain, short lead times are necessary to lower production costs and provide a possible competitive advantage. Because of its significant reliance on fossil fuels and non-renewable resources, the logistics sector has been under increasing pressure to address environmental sustainability. This circumstance necessitates taking action for efficient logistics and transportation as well as appropriate environmental management. The Ethiopian economy relies on agriculture, and the sector is important for addressing food security and earning foreign exchange. Agricultural products such as coffee, oilseed, and pulses are the dominant export logistics. Being in such agricultural economic activity, the country faces multifaceted trade logistics challenges. Logistics and agriculture are designated as the main priority intervention sectors in order to boost production and accomplish import substitution. Even though few studies attempted to disclose logistics performance and related challenges in the Ethiopian context, there is still a reasonable gap in empirically investigating the impact of logistics activities on agriculture. The study gap also pertains to the idea of environmental sustainability. Thus, the purpose of this study was to empirically investigate how export-import logistics operations affect agriculture with environmental sustainability concepts.

The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model was used to explore the impact of logistics activities on agricultural development, while time series plots are utilized for trend analysis of the agriculture GDP and CO₂ emissions from transport. Preliminary trend analysis indicates that although the agriculture sector is the main driver of overall economic growth, its percentage of Ethiopia's GDP is declining. Periodic drought, deforestation, overgrazing, and seasonal rainfall are the main problems facing Ethiopian agriculture. The fastest-growing industry in Ethiopia is the service sector, which is surpassing the GDP of agriculture. However, the trend of carbon dioxide emissions from transportation is quickly growing. This dramatic increase in transportation-related carbon dioxide emissions has certain detrimental effects on environmental sustainability since it traps heat in the atmosphere. In countries like Ethiopia where green logistics and transportation are not practiced, this is a burdensome consequence. Ethiopian logistics are

characterized by manual procedures; there is a shortage of temperature-controlled silos and a centralized warehouse system.

The result further shows that there exists a negative long-run relationship between agricultural development and logistics activities such as carbon dioxide emission from transport and merchandise trade. Merchandise export is considered to capture the monetary value of export logistics and found to have a positive long-run relationship with agricultural development. Merchandise imports, which reflect the monetary value of import logistics, have a positive relationship with agricultural development in the short run. In countries where imports exceed exports, such as in the Ethiopian economy, a trade deficit is anticipated. The Ethiopian government gives priority to agriculture and logistics because these two sectors are the backbone of the country's economy. The Ethiopian Agricultural Transformation Agency started a digital initiative to map all of the country's soil resources and establish a national soil information database. This is a good step to promote the Ethiopian agriculture toward the sustainable development goals. Regarding logistics service, the government set a ten-year national logistics strategic plan to improve the performance and operation of the sector. However, lack of information technology and lack of information exchange supported by the information technology are identified as a gap in Ethiopian logistics sector.

The authors' contribution in the current study lies in the design of the empirical approach to fulfil the quantitative research gap in Ethiopian agro-logistics sectors for better policy decision-making. As part of recommendations, the agricultural initiatives that have been recently started by the Agricultural Transformation Agency should be attentively implemented to recover the falling of agriculture share in GDP. Export logistics should be increased for import substitution to manage trade deficit. Integration of digital technology and implementation of green logistics and transport are needed for logistics sectors as environmental sustainability matters.